

Turing Algorithm: Simulating Organic Morphogenesis through Data Structures

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Abstract

This article presents the process of creating an interactive algorithm developed in JavaScript, stemming from the Data Morphogenesis course at ECA-USP (2025). Based on Alan Turing's studies on morphogenesis — particularly his 1954 paper *The Chemical Basis of Morphogenesis* — and on the behavior of the organism *Physarum polycephalum* (slime mold), we implemented a generative system in JavaScript using the p5.js library.

This study connects Turing's reaction-diffusion principles with the spatial growth and navigation mechanisms of *Physarum*, transposing them into a digital interactive environment. The system reproduces three essential features of the biological organism: (1) local gradient sensing, (2) trail deposition with spatial memory, and (3) a dynamic of decay and diffusion.

Beyond its technical aspects, the article seeks to contribute to contemporary debates on nature and culture by exploring this system as a tool for investigating biomorphic patterns in generative art and for developing interactive bioinformational installations.

The results demonstrate how basic biological principles can give rise to complex emergent behaviors, offering new perspectives for artistic creation in the digital age. Ultimately, the work connects art, science, and technology, proposing a morphogenetic approach to contemporary aesthetic production.

Keywords: computational morphogenesis, Alan Turing, *Physarum polycephalum*, generative art, complex systems, bioinformation, bioart.

Fig 2: Interface principal do algoritmo;

Fig. 3: Imagem gerada

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Anexo I: Galeria

<https://youtu.be/FEG2Aq9gfpA>

<https://youtu.be/7EBpVwf17N4>

<https://youtu.be/61viKZwQyDA>

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